

ADAPTING TO FESTIVAL DOWNTIMES: MARKETING STRATEGIES OF LOCAL BUSINESSES DURING THE MORIONES FESTIVAL OFF-PEAK SEASON IN MARINDUQUE, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

The Moriones Festival is a major cultural event in the province of Marinduque, Philippines that attracts many tourists each year. While it boosts local income during Holy Week, many small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) struggle during the off-peak months from May to February. This study explores the marketing strategies these businesses use to cope with seasonal downturns. Using a qualitative case study with a descriptive approach, the research focused on selected hotels, restaurants, souvenir shops, and a tour agency. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with ten business owners or representatives and two government officials from the Provincial Tourism and Cultural Office and the Department of Trade and Industry – Marinduque. Promotional materials were also reviewed to support data triangulation. Thematic analysis was applied to identify common patterns and key themes. Findings reveal that businesses face reduced demand, financial strain, workforce adjustments, changing consumer behavior, and limited institutional support during off-peak seasons. To respond, many adjust their product offerings, revise pricing, strengthen promotions, and expand digital marketing efforts. Diversifying services, improving online presence, and building stronger collaboration with government agencies emerged as important strategies. Overall, the study highlights practical approaches that can help SMEs maintain operations, stabilize revenue, and support year-round tourism development in Marinduque.

Keywords: *Moriones Festival, off-peak season, local businesses, marketing strategies, tourism*

INTRODUCTION

Festivals play an important role in preserving culture and supporting economic growth. Around the world, they attract tourists, increase visitor spending, create jobs, and provide exposure for local businesses. In countries with rich traditions like the Philippines, festivals go beyond celebration—they serve as vital economic lifelines for many communities. They contribute to tourism income and provide opportunities to showcase local products, crafts, food, and heritage. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO, 2022), cultural tourism, including festivals, is one of the fastest-growing segments of global tourism.

At the national level, the Philippine Department of Tourism (DOT) and the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) recognize festivals as strong economic drivers. These agencies support local governments and small businesses through tourism campaigns, skills training, and marketing assistance. For instance, the DOT has promoted lesser-known regional festivals to help spread tourist arrivals more evenly throughout the year (Cawis, 2025). Meanwhile, the DTI supports micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) through programs like One Town, One Product (OTOP) and local trade fairs (Department of Trade and Industry, 2021). Despite these efforts, many businesses that rely on festival tourism still face challenges related to seasonality.

A clear example is the Moriones Festival in the province of Marinduque, a long-standing cultural and religious celebration held during Holy Week. Known for its Roman soldier masks and the dramatization of Saint Longinus' story, the festival draws a large number of tourists and pilgrims from March to April. During this period, hotels, restaurants, souvenir shops, and tour operators experience a sharp rise in sales, often depending on this short but intense season to sustain them for the rest of the year (Roam Leisurely, n.d.).

Research shows that festivals create temporary economic boosts by increasing demand in accommodation, food, retail, and tour services (Getz, 2010). Similar patterns can be seen in other Philippine festivals such as Lucban's Pahiyas and Laguna's Anilag Festival, where SMEs report higher sales and increased economic activity during event periods (Ortozo, 2024; Francisco, 2024). In Marinduque, tourist arrivals reportedly increased by 80% in the first quarter of 2024 compared to 2023 (Philippine News Agency, 2024).

Beyond immediate income, festivals also support employment and entrepreneurship, creating both direct and indirect jobs in services and event-related activities (Quinn, 2006). They also help strengthen place identity and promote destinations to wider audiences (Palmer & Richards, 2010). The Moriones Festival, for

example, enhances Marinduque's visibility and introduces visitors to its cultural heritage and natural attractions (TaasNooPilipino, n.d.).

However, festivals also bring challenges, especially related to seasonality. High visitor numbers during peak periods can strain infrastructure and public services (Andersson & Lundberg, 2013; Francisco, 2024). In contrast, off-peak seasons often result in reduced income, underemployment, and underused facilities. Similar issues have been observed internationally, such as the projected economic losses following the cancellation of Queensland's 2025 Big Red Bash (MDPI, 2022; Courier Mail, 2024). Marinduque faces comparable seasonal fluctuations, with tourist arrivals declining outside the Moriones Festival period (Philippine News Agency, 2024).

To address off-peak challenges, businesses locally and abroad have adopted various marketing strategies. Some destinations create unique off-season experiences, such as themed tours or seasonal packages (Tourism Tasmania, 2023; Balanced Tourism, 2024). In the Philippines, creative packages like discounted "Rainy Day Getaway" promotions have been used to maintain bookings during slower months (Allora Linen, 2023). Collaboration is also important, with bundled tourism packages and partnerships helping spread tourist spending and encourage longer stays (Destination Boost, 2023; Belandres et.al., 2024). Flexible booking options and digital marketing efforts further support off-season visibility (Boost Brands, 2022; Exceptional Experiences, 2023; Mercado & Villanueva, 2022).

Although these strategies show promising results, there is limited research focusing specifically on how businesses in Marinduque manage off-peak periods. Most studies focus on peak-season impacts, leaving off-season dynamics less explored. There is also limited understanding of how SMEs adjust their marketing mix—such as product offerings, pricing, distribution channels and promotions—during slower months.

Addressing these gaps is important for developing practical policies and strategies that promote year-round tourism stability, economic resilience, and community well-being. This study aimed to explore these off-peak marketing strategies in Marinduque and contribute to more balanced and sustainable tourism development.

Research Questions

The study aimed to achieve its general objective of exploring the marketing strategies of local businesses in Marinduque during the off-peak seasons of the Moriones Festival by focusing specifically on the following objectives:

1. How participants describe the challenges encountered among local businesses for the Moriones Festival during off-peak season?
2. How participants describe the scenarios of local businesses for Moriones festival during off-peak season in terms of:
 - 2.1. Product and service offering;
 - 2.2. Pricing strategy;

- 2.3. Distribution channels; and
- 2.4. Promotional efforts?
- 3. How participants identify alternative opportunities among local businesses for the Moriones festival during off-peak seasons in terms of:
 - 3.1. Product and service offering;
 - 3.2. Pricing strategy;
 - 3.3. Distribution channels; and
 - 3.4. Promotional efforts?
- 4. How can marketing strategies be developed for local businesses based on the research findings, in terms of:
 - 4.1. Product and service offering;
 - 4.2. Pricing strategy;
 - 4.3. Distribution channels; and
 - 4.4. Promotional efforts?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study used a qualitative approach to understand the experiences of local business owners during the off-peak season of the Moriones Festival in Marinduque. Qualitative research is appropriate for exploring social and cultural factors influencing decision-making (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016), showing how entrepreneurs adjust marketing strategies when tourist demand declines. A descriptive design was also applied to present current marketing practices, capturing product, pricing, distribution, and promotional strategies without manipulating variables (Kumar, 2011).

Locale of the Study. The research was conducted in Marinduque, Philippines, focusing on tourism-related businesses during the off-peak months from May to February, when tourist arrivals are generally lower. Affected businesses included hotels, resorts, restaurants, souvenir shops, and tour agencies.

Tradition of Inquiry. A case study approach was employed to gain deeper insight into how businesses manage marketing strategies during the off-season. According to Hoover (2021), case studies examine a person, group, or community using multiple data sources. This approach enabled an in-depth look at participants' challenges, decisions, and strategies in real-life settings.

Sampling Method and Respondents. Purposive sampling was used to select twelve participants with direct experience managing tourism-related businesses during off-peak periods. Participants included ten business owners or representatives from hotels, restaurants, souvenir shops, and a tour agency, and two tourism officials from the Provincial Tourism and Cultural Office and the Department of Trade and Industry – Marinduque. Businesses were small to medium-sized (2–35 employees) and operated for more than one year. Demographic data collected included role, years of experience, business operation length, and number of employees. Pseudonyms were used for

business participants to ensure confidentiality, while tourism officials' names were disclosed with consent.

Data Gathering Procedure. Data were collected primarily through semi-structured interviews using open-ended questions with follow-up probes (Ho & Limpaecher, 2022). Interviews covered marketing strategies, operational challenges, coping practices, and sustainability measures, and were conducted face-to-face with consent for recording and transcription. Document analysis of brochures, flyers, and online promotions supported and validated interview data.

Research Instrument. The main tool was a researcher-designed semi-structured interview guide, validated by three experts in tourism, marketing, and qualitative research. Questions focused on marketing mix elements, off-peak challenges, coping strategies, and business opportunities. Its flexible format allowed participants to share experiences while keeping discussions aligned with the study objectives.

Data Analysis. Thematic analysis was used to review and code transcribed interviews, identifying patterns and grouping related codes into broader themes on challenges, marketing strategies, and adaptation practices. Findings were compared with documents to enhance credibility.

Scope and Limitations. The study explored marketing strategies of hotels, restaurants, souvenir shops, and a tour agency in Marinduque during the off-peak months from May to February, focusing on products, pricing, distribution, and promotions. Limitations include the small purposive sample, subjective experiences, and exclusion of broader external factors such as economic trends, disasters, or policy changes. Findings may not generalize to other regions or festivals but provide insights into managing seasonal fluctuations in a festival-driven economy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Challenges Encountered Among Local Businesses for the Moriones Festival During Off-Peak Season

Low Customer Demand and Occupancy. During the off-peak season, local business owners and hotel operators experience reduced demand and occupancy, affecting revenue and operations. Grace, a hotel owner, said, "*Hindi kami nawawalan ng client, pero hindi like peak na full*" ("We don't run out of clients, but it's not like the peak season when it's full"), demonstrating structural resilience (Hall & Williams, 2002). Angel, a hotel manager, noted, "*Sobrang hirap makahatak talaga ng (mga) guests... so one is low occupancy*" ("It's really hard to attract guests... one issue is low occupancy"), highlighting the need for marketing, product innovation, and added value (Crouch & Ritchie, 2003). Nicole, a hotel resort representative, remarked, "*Sobrang onti (guests), pero normal sa 'min*" ("There are very few guests, but it's normal for us"), reflecting

acceptance of seasonality and planning for long-term competitiveness (Dwyer & Kim, 2003).

Reduced Sales, Financial Instability, and Seasonal Income Fluctuations.

Local businesses face financial challenges due to lower sales, unstable income, and reliance on festival periods. Andrea, an operations and marketing head, stated, "*Ayun, mabagal ang benta*" ("Sales are slow"), consistent with Getz and Nilsson (2004) on unpredictable income in seasonal enterprises. Mr. Labay observed, "*Basta kung kelan ang Holy Week, diyan ka nagpi-peak... biglang siyang (kita) bababa*" ("Income peaks during Holy Week, then drops sharply"), reflecting Butler's (2001) "boom-bust" cycle. Ms. Garnier noted, "*Kapag trend, na tuwing December, January tumataas siya, February, wala. Bagsak*" ("Sales rise in December and January, then fall in February"), confirming seasonal patterns among MSMEs (Amsden & McEntee, 2016).

Cost Reduction and Workforce Challenges. Businesses manage financial pressure through labor adjustments. Angel explained, "*...kapag talagang low occupancy... skeletal workforce... take 2 days-off muna... no work, no pay*" ("Smaller team; some staff take extra unpaid days off"), aligning with Baum (2011) on reducing shifts during slow periods. Nicole stated, "*...magbabawas kami ng tao, kasi ang mahal ng tao na pinapasahod*" ("We reduce staff because payroll is costly"), supporting Lashley and Lee-Ross (2012). Camille shared, "*...nagka-conduct kami ng double-off... para maulan 'yung labor cost namin*" ("Extra unpaid days off to reduce labor costs"), reflecting Ioannides and Zampoukos (2011) on flexible scheduling.

Uneven Revenue Distribution and Government Support. Tensions exist between business owners and government institutions over income and support. Grace stated, "*...ang income ay less... kasi hindi patas ang distribusyon... walang income kasi ina-kanya ng gobyerno... ngayon wala na kami*" ("Income is lower because distribution is unfair; the government took it"), aligning with Cole (2006) on top-down tourism planning marginalizing local communities. Ms. Garnier highlighted resource constraints: "*Yung lugar na kung saan nila ina-market 'yung kanilang mga product, kulang... kapag ang target mo ay local*" ("Marketing spaces are insufficient"), consistent with Rogerson (2008) on inadequate infrastructure limiting small businesses.

Shift in Consumer Behavior and Lack of Local Appreciation. Government representatives noted low local demand for culturally themed products outside the festival period. Ms. Garnier stated, "*Yung mga locals hindi masyadong... appreciative... Mabili ka baga ng bag na may pintura na moryon?*" ("Locals aren't very appreciative; would they buy a Morion-designed bag?"), supporting Richards (2006) on limited local engagement with tourist-oriented products. Mr. Labay added, "*Normally... the common products you're selling are Moriones-inspired... nawawala 'yun outside of the season*" ("Moriones-inspired products disappear outside the season"), reflecting the seasonality of heritage tourism (Nyaupane & Timothy, 2006). These factors limit sales opportunities and challenge the sustainability of heritage-based enterprises.

2. Scenarios of Local Businesses for Moriones Festival During Off-Peak Season

2.1. Product and Service Offering

Product/Service Consistency. Local businesses in Marinduque maintain consistent products and services to ensure customer satisfaction during the off-peak season. Grace, a hotel owner, stated, *“Ako ay naka-standard ang empleyado”* (“I maintain standard staffing”), reflecting the importance of consistent service and workforce in fostering customer loyalty (Bowen et al., 2021). Nicole, from a hotel resort, commented, *“Ganun pa rin”* (“Still the same”), supporting Grönroos (2000) on maintaining service levels year-round. Similarly, Camille, a restaurant manager, said, *“Wala, Ma’am. Same lang po”* (“Menu remains unchanged”), which aligns with the findings of Bitner et al. (2017) on consistency promoting customer trust and loyalty.

Adjustments in Product/Service Quantity. To manage lower demand, businesses reduce quantities while maintaining variety. Andrea, a restaurant manager, explained, *“Naga-bawas kami...pag bilang ay ‘yung mahina. Naga-bawas kami ng luto”* (“We reduce servings when customer numbers are low”). Kristine, a restaurant owner, noted, *“Kapag off-peak, lesser lang din ang quantity ng luto, pero ‘yung dami ng putahe, still the same”* (“Portions are smaller, but the menu variety remains”), reflecting resource optimization strategies (Jones & Lockwood, 2002).

Diversification of Product Offerings. Businesses also diversify offerings to attract customers. Janelle, a souvenir shop owner, stated, *“Ako ay naga-innovate lagi... naga-ano ako ng peanut cookies, mga kung anu-anong pwedeng idagdag”* (“I continuously innovate... adding peanut cookies and other items”), supporting Kim & Lee (2019) on product innovation during low seasons. Mae adds seasonal or in-demand items: *“Bukod sa ‘ming mga gawa, nag-aangkat o sumusubok kami ng iba’t ibang mga paninda na patok sa mga ganung season”* (“We import or test items popular in that season”), consistent with Navata (n.d.) on flexible inventory. Mr. Labay noted that some hotels offer MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions) services: *“Nagiging convention center na rin siya, MICE facility”* (“It functions as a convention center”), aligning with the California Lodging Investment Conference (2023) on diversification for steady revenue.

Seasonal Offerings and Special Promotions. Hotels and tour agencies employ special promotions to maintain engagement. Angel, a hotel manager, said, *“Pag Holy Week naga-add lang kami ng... welcome amenities. Pero ginagawa na rin namin ‘yung sa ibang guests kahit off-peak”* (“We add amenities during Holy Week and for other guests during off-peak”), supporting Dwyer and Kim (2010) on enhancing competitiveness through added services. Jean, a travel and tour officer, noted expanded offerings: *“May mga services pang inooffer... like educational tours, event planning, local and international tour packages, airline ticketing, hotel reservations, and transportation,”* consistent with Horner and Swarbrooke (2007) on diversifying services to attract broader clients.

Focus on Local and Staple Products. Businesses maintain staple products to ensure familiarity and steady demand. Kristine, a restaurant owner, stated, “*Ngayon ang regular na lang namin... kare-kare, menudo... pork liver steak... lumpiang sariwa*” (“We serve expected regular dishes”), reflecting Cohen and Avieli (2004) on traditional foods fostering loyalty. Erika, a souvenir shop owner, sells year-round Moriones-themed items: “*Mga t-shirts, mugs... magnetic items*” (“T-shirts, mugs, and magnets”), which Swanson and Timothy (2012) identify as culturally significant products that maintain consumer interest.

Online and Delivery Services. Digital platforms and delivery services help sustain revenue during off-peak periods. Janelle uses online sales: “*Oo. Meron online... ’yun ngang kaka-deliver laang kahapon*” (“We have online sales, like a recent delivery”), aligning with UNWTO (2022) on digital transformation for small businesses. Camille delivers to nearby municipalities: “*Nagde-deliver po kami near the municipality like Mogpog, Gasan,*” supporting Dennis et al. (2020) on stabilizing revenue via delivery. Andrea offers catering: “*Naga-deliver kami... may mga catering po kami*” (“We provide delivery and catering”), consistent with Buhalis and Foerste (2015) on personalized services enhancing resilience.

2.2. Pricing Strategy

Discounting and Price Reduction. To address low demand during the off-peak season, businesses implement targeted discounts and promotions. Grace, a hotel owner, explained: “*Minsan ay less than 10%. May mga promo-promo rin. Minsan ang mga senior ay discounted*” (“Sometimes it’s less than 10%. There are promotions. Seniors get discounts”), using customer segmentation to attract specific groups (Kimes, 2011). Angel, another hotel manager, noted: “*Kapag low season, automatic kailangan mong magbaba... ’pag peak, zero. We don’t give any discount*” (“Prices are lowered in low season, full price during peak”), demonstrating seasonal price adjustments to optimize revenue (Hayes & Miller, 2011). Ms. Garniel observed that some businesses offer creative deals like BOGO to boost sales: “*Yung iba talaga inababa ’yung price o kaya nagkakaroon sila special offers... buy-one, get ganito*” (“Some lower prices or offer special deals”), aligning with the findings of Bowen et al. (2016) on promotions enhancing customer interest.

Price Increases in Certain Areas. Some businesses raise prices due to demand or operational costs. Nicole, a hotel resort representative, said: “*Hindi rin kami nagbababa ng price... Dati P50... ngayon P75, nighttime P100*” (“We don’t lower prices but increased them; P50 → P75, nighttime P100”), reflecting dynamic pricing during peak periods (McMahon-Beattie & Yeoman, 2011). Erika, a souvenir shop owner, cited costs: “*Medyo mataas kami... nagbabayad kami sa booth, tapos may iba-ibang charges pa*” (“Prices are higher due to booth fees and other charges”), consistent with Marshall et al. (2015) on overhead-driven price adjustments.

Static Pricing with Minor Adjustments. Local food businesses maintain generally stable prices, adjusting only for supply cost changes. Andrea, restaurant

operations head, explained: *“Hindi kami naga-taas... nung nag-taas ng mga bilingin, nag-dagdag din kami ng P5 o P10”* (“Prices mostly stable; slight increases when ingredient costs rise”), supporting Barrett (2016). Camille shared: *“Same lang... Naga-change lang kapag may market price increase”* (“Prices change only when market costs rise”), and Kristine added: *“Ay hindi naman. Naga-vary ‘yan, ‘yung prices kasi is magkano ‘yung bili. So, for example, kapag mahal ‘yung fish”* (“Prices vary depending on ingredient cost, e.g., if fish is expensive”), as mentioned by Linder (2021), these minor adjustments balance affordability with profitability.

Package Deals and Special Offers. Businesses use package deals and seasonal promotions to attract customers. Jean, a travel agency officer, explained: *“Price rates... naka-depende sa package... mas marami kayong magbo-book, mas makaka-discount kayo”* (“Group bookings receive larger discounts”), demonstrating tiered pricing to encourage volume (Berry, 2018). Camille highlighted event-based promotions: *“Tapos more on mga combos and promos kami, like ngayon, parating na ‘yung Valentine’s...”* (“Then, we focus on combos and promos, like now, Valentine’s is coming...”), reflecting strategies to increase sales during specific periods (Chef Works Blog, 2016).

Pricing Strategies Based on Demand and Supply. Businesses adjust prices following supply-demand principles. Mr. Labay from the Provincial Tourism and Cultural Office explained: *“Dapat bababa siya... may off-season prices”* (“Prices should decrease; resorts offer off-season rates”), showing use of discounts and perks to attract customers (Keller & Kotler, 2016). Such strategies ensure competitiveness, stabilize revenue, and maintain customer engagement during low-demand periods.

2.3. Distribution Channels

Digital Presence and Online Platforms. Local businesses in Marinduque increasingly use social media to engage customers and improve visibility. Grace, a hotel owner, shared: *“Meron (Facebook). Kaya lang ay hindi pa ‘yung sa website”* (“We have Facebook; no website yet”), reflecting the trend of starting with social media (Acenero et al., 2024). Angel added: *“Meron pong Facebook page ang Balar... and we also have Instagram... Actually, they have the option of booking online”* (“Balar has a Facebook page and Instagram... they even have online booking”), showing integration of promotion, customer service, and online booking (Borlio et al., 2020). Nicole and Andrea confirmed using Facebook for reservations and marketing, aligning with Amadora (2023) who found 67% of Filipino small businesses use social media for sales and engagement. Janelle noted online platforms also support deliveries: *“Oo. Meron online... ‘yun ngang kaka-deliver laang kahapon”* (“Yes, we have online orders... just like the delivery we had yesterday”), improving efficiency (Acenero et al., 2024).

Catering and Delivery Services. Restaurants expand reach through delivery and catering. Andrea stated: *“Naga-deliver kami... may mga catering po kami”* (“We do deliveries... and we also offer catering”), while Camille highlighted province-wide service: *“Buong Marinduque pwede”* (“We deliver anywhere in Marinduque”). Kristine added: *“Nag-ooffer kami ng delivery at catering services”* (“We offer delivery and catering

services”), showing flexibility in serving both individual and group orders. These practices align with Transportify (2023), emphasizing the role of off-site services in maintaining revenue and meeting customer demand.

Wholesale and Export Channels. Souvenir shops use wholesale and export to maintain income during low tourist traffic. Mae explained: *“May mga bumibili sa ‘min ng wholesale at inabenta naman nila”* (“Some people buy from us wholesale and then resell”), while Erika shared past export partnerships: *“Lokal laang, pero may exporter kami noon rito. Sila ang naga-dala. Kami ang supplier”* (“It was local only, but we had an exporter here before. They handled delivery; we were the supplier”) (DTI, 2021). These strategies diversify markets and provide stability during off-peak periods.

Trade Fairs and External Market Engagement. Participation in trade fairs allows businesses to reach new markets. Ms. Garniel noted: *“...nasali sila sa mga trade fair sa ibang lugar... Ilocos, Baguio... napunta sila kung saan may market”* (“They participated in trade fairs in other places... Ilocos, Baguio... wherever there was a market”) (DTI, 2021), highlighting trade fairs as effective tools for SME promotion and brand growth.

Local Distribution Channels. Despite these strategies, many small businesses still rely on local sales. Erika noted: *“Lokal laang, pero may exporter kami noon rito”* (“We mainly sell locally, although we had an exporter before”), reflecting common rural challenges such as limited transport, infrastructure, and access to wider markets (FAO, n.d.).

2.4. Promotional Efforts

Digital Marketing and Social Media. Social media is central for visibility during off-peak seasons. Grace said: *“Meron (Facebook). Kaya lang ay hindi pa ‘yung sa website”* (“We have Facebook; no website yet”), while Angel added: *“Meron pong Facebook page... and Instagram”* (“We have a Facebook page... and Instagram”), showing multi-platform engagement (BusinessWorld Online, 2023). Restaurants and souvenir shops also use social media for promotions, with Camille stating: *“...nagpo-post sila sa social media...”* (“They post on social media”), and Kristine: *“Social media ang key”* (“Social media is the key”), reflecting its importance in customer engagement and sales (Fronza et al., 2024).

Discounts, Promotions, and Special Offers. Discounts and promotions attract customers when foot traffic is low. Angel: *“Automatic we give price discounts”* (“We automatically give price discounts”) (Frothingham, 2024); Mae: *“Naga-bigay kami ng freebies o discounts”* (“We give freebies or discounts”) (Hostaway, n.d.); Janelle: *“May mga discount kami”* (“We have discounts”) (Travel Trade Maldives, 2023). Mr. Labay added: *“Dapat lumalabas din ang perks, mga discount... sa mga resort”* (“Perks and discounts should also be offered at resorts”), showing public support for promotions (DTI, 2022).

Traditional Marketing Methods (Flyers, Print Ads, and Tarpaulins). Flyers, print ads, and tarpaulins remain relevant. Nicole: *“Merong mga flyers... Mas gusto niya tarpaulin”* (“We have flyers... he prefers tarpaulins”), Angel: *“...naka-identify naman po dun kung off-peak o peak”* (“It’s indicated there whether it’s off-peak or peak”) (Kutev, 2025; Scott, 2023). These methods complement digital efforts, especially for local audiences and tourists unfamiliar with the area.

Word of Mouth and Customer Referrals. Personal recommendations strongly influence customer behavior. Kristine shared: *“...may isang group ng riders... ‘Uy, sa’n kayo kumakain?’ ‘Ah, ang pinupuntahan agad namin ay (pangalan ng kainan).”* (“A group of riders came and asked, ‘Where do you eat?’ ‘Oh, we always go to (name of the restaurant).”). This illustrates how word-of-mouth functions as a cost-effective promotional tool for local businesses (Jalilvand, 2017).

Trade Fairs and Expos. Participation in external events expands market reach. Ms. Garniel explained: *“...nasali sila sa mga trade fair sa ibang lugar... Ilocos, Baguio”* (“They participated in trade fairs in other places... Ilocos, Baguio”), with DTI providing logistics support like accommodation, transportation, booth fees, and product transport (DTI, 2022; DTI, 2024). Trade fairs help businesses grow and maintain visibility when local tourism is low.

3. Alternative Opportunities Among Local Businesses for the Moriones Festival During Off-Peak Seasons

3.1. Product and Service Offering

Introducing New Activities and Experiences. To attract more visitors during the Moriones Festival, local businesses in Marinduque could offer unique activities that make the experience more fun and memorable. Angel, a hotel manager, pointed out the lack of guest activities and shared her idea: *“Plan ko mag-create ng something like Zumba para sa mga guests, saka yoga... activities na pwedeng mag-encourage sa kanila na ‘Uy, tara, subukan natin ‘tong activity, wala pang ibang nag-ooffer.”* (“I plan to create something like Zumba and yoga for guests... activities that might encourage them to try something no one else is offering.”) This shows how simple but fresh experiences can attract more guests (Fyall et al., 2012). Ms. Garniel from DTI also emphasized that experience is key: *“Kailangang meron kang attraction... Tourism is about experience...”* (“You need to have an attraction... Tourism is about experience...”), highlighting the importance of engaging visitors through experiences rather than just products or services (Gilmore & Pine, 2021).

Improving Service and Customer Experience. Improving service quality can enhance visitor experiences during the Moriones Festival. Camille, a restaurant manager, shared: *“Kailangan po agad ng staff ay proper training, customer service training... Kapag maganda ‘yung service, hindi lang naman kasi food e, ‘yung dining experience din.”* (“Staff really need proper training, especially in customer service... When the service is good, it’s not just about the food, but also the dining experience.”) Well-trained, friendly staff can improve customer satisfaction and leave lasting positive impressions (Bitner et al., 2018).

Diversifying Tour Services. To maintain interest and income beyond Moriones, local tourism providers could diversify services. Jean, a travel agency officer, said: *“Kaya nga importante na to add services bukod sa mga package tuwing Moryonan, katulad ng mga educational tours, events planning, local and international tour packages, domestic and international airline ticketing...”* (“It’s important to offer services beyond Moriones packages, like educational tours, event planning, tour packages, and airline ticketing.”) Offering both logistics and unique experiences helps attract a wider audience and improve satisfaction (Buhalis & Law, 2008).

3.2. Pricing Strategy

Local businesses have not explored alternative pricing strategies for the Moriones off-peak season, as current methods are seen as effective for reduced demand. Businesses stick to familiar pricing strategies, showing a preference for stability and reliability (Keller & Kotler, 2016).

3.3. Distribution channels

Digitalization and Online Presence. Digitalization can help local businesses expand reach and visibility. Angel, a hotel manager, shared: *“I think kailangan na ding magkaroon ng own website ang Balar. ‘Yung ‘yung wala pa kami. Actually, wino-work-out na rin siya ni Madam, to create our own website... kasi meron na kasi ngayon na website na they can book na their ano directly.”* (“I think the hotel also needs its own website... Madam is already working on it to create our own website... because now there are websites where they can book directly.”) Websites reduce reliance on third-party platforms and increase profitability (Buhalis & Law, 2008). Ms. Garniel emphasized: *“E-commerce talaga ang ano. Mag-o-online na talaga sila.”* (“E-commerce really is the way to go. They really need to go online.”) She added: *“Mas mawa-widen ‘yung market mo na mari-reach nila kapag nag-digitalize sila ng kanilang negosyo. Kumbaga hindi taga-Marinduque ang target nila doon. Malawak pa.”* (“The wider the market they can reach when they digitalize their business. It’s not just targeting people from Marinduque. It can go beyond that.”) Digital platforms help reach both local and international customers (Tiago & Verissimo, 2014).

Expanding Business Partnerships. Expanding partnerships can support MSME growth. Ms. Garniel explained: *“Hanap pa sila ng partner sa kabila. Kasi po Ma’am ‘yung isa kong kakilala. Nakakatuwa kasi meat products naman po siya... hindi siya tumigil kasi may ano eh, may market siya sa kabila...”* (“They need to find a partner elsewhere. One of my acquaintances sells meat products and didn’t stop because they had a market elsewhere.”) Strategic partnerships help access new markets, share resources, and improve resilience (Gnyawali & Park, 2009).

3.4. Promotional Efforts

Social Media and Online Marketing. Local businesses could leverage social media during off-peak seasons. Angel said: *“Siguro more of advertising online... kasi ako,*

I'm working consistently on sa consistency na posting sa Facebook page, kasi the more na nagpo-post ka, the more na nakikilala ka... ("Maybe more on online advertising... I'm working consistently on posting on our Facebook page, because the more you post, the more people recognize you.") Nicole added: *"Ayun, sinasabi ko na magkaroon ng pictures and videos for promotion (in Facebook)."* ("We need to have pictures and videos for promotion (on Facebook).") Mr. Labay highlighted: *"Dapat makasabay sila sa electronic marketing... social media. Dapat may ganun sila. Malaking bagay 'yun."* ("They should keep up with electronic marketing... social media. They should have that. It's a big deal.") Regular posting and visual content increase engagement and brand recognition (Ashley et al., 2013; Hudecova, n.d.; Tiago & Veríssimo, 2014).

Website Development and E-Commerce. A dedicated website and e-commerce platform provide growth opportunities. Angel stated: *"Siguro, kailangan na ni Balar na magkaroon ng sariling website... Inaasikaso na siya ni Madam... marami na rin kasi na sa websites nagbo-book."* ("I think Balar also needs to have its own website... Madam is already working on it... because now there are websites where they can book directly.") This shows how a professional website builds credibility and allows direct bookings (Bortnikov, 2024). Ms. Garniel emphasized: *"E-commerce talaga ang ano. Mag-o-online na talaga sila."* ("E-commerce really is the way to go... The wider the market they can reach when they digitalize their business.") Online platforms help small businesses reach wider, even global markets (Tendoku, n.d.).

Partnerships for Promotion. Collaborations with government, NGOs, and private companies support promotion. Grace said: *"Ang kailangan kasi ay partner dapat. Kasi kapag nasa probinsya, partner talaga, government and NGOs, private-public relationship."* ("What we need is a partner. Because when you're in the province, partnership really matters. Government and NGOs, a private-public relationship.") Such partnerships provide resources, reach, and promotion (Buhalis, 2000).

Consistency and Engagement. Active social media presence is vital for off-peak engagement. Angel shared: *"The more na nagpo-post ka, the more na nakikilala ka, pero kung halimbawa sa isang linggo, bihira ka lang mag-post, parang konti lang din 'yung ano mo, viewers, 'yung audience."* ("The more you post, the more you're recognized. But if, for example, you only post rarely in a week, your viewers and audience will be limited.") Nicole added: *"Ngayon sigurong season, magiging pa-active kami (sa Facebook)"* ("Now, for this season, we will try to be more active on Facebook"). Consistent posting builds brand awareness and loyalty (De Vries et al., 2012; Kumar & Shah, 2004).

Promoting the Region Beyond the Moriones Festival. Promoting Marinduque year-round helps reduce reliance on peak events. Mr. Labay said: *"Actually, ang trend ngayon is they try to sell the province, Marinduque beyond Moriones. That's what they do..."* ("Actually, the trend now is they try to sell the province, Marinduque, beyond Moriones. That's what they do...") Diversifying tourism offerings stabilizes the economy and attracts visitors year-round (McKercher & du Cros, 2002).

4. Marketing Strategies that can be Developed for Local Businesses for the Moriones Festival During Off-Peak Seasons

A. Hotels

4.1. Product and Service Offering

- Introduce off-peak experiential activities (e.g., Zumba, yoga sessions, cultural workshops, farm tours, local cooking demonstrations).
- Position properties as MICE-ready venues (meetings, trainings, small conventions).
- Develop themed weekend packages (wellness weekends, couple retreats, barkada packages).
- Enhance customer service training to strengthen guest satisfaction and encourage repeat visits.
- Offer year-round Marinduque experience packages, not just Moriones-focused stays.

4.2. Pricing Strategy

- Implement seasonal pricing tiers (clear off-peak vs. peak rates).
- Offer value-added pricing instead of heavy discounting (free breakfast, welcome amenities, late check-out).
- Create bundle pricing (accommodation + tour + dining discounts).
- Provide group and corporate rates for seminars and institutional bookings.
- Maintain transparent pricing while allowing slight flexibility during low occupancy periods.

4.3. Distribution Channels

- Develop official websites with direct booking systems to reduce third-party dependency.
- Maximize Facebook, Instagram, and booking platforms for reservations.
- Partner with local tour agencies and event organizers.
- Collaborate with government and NGOs for institutional events.
- Utilize email marketing and messenger-based inquiries for customer retention.

4.4. Promotional Efforts

- Maintain consistent social media posting (photos, testimonials, short-form videos).
- Promote Marinduque as a year-round destination, not only during Moriones.
- Offer limited-time off-peak promos (weekday specials).
- Use both digital ads and traditional materials (tarpaulins, flyers).

- Encourage word-of-mouth marketing through referral incentives.

B. Restaurants

4.1. Product and Service Offering

- Maintain staple Filipino dishes while introducing seasonal or limited-time menu items.
- Offer combo meals, family bundles, and barkada platters.
- Expand catering and packed meal services.
- Improve service quality and dining experience through staff training.
- Introduce food-based experiences (food tasting nights, local cuisine promotion).

4.2. Pricing Strategy

- Keep prices generally stable; adjust only for raw material fluctuations.
- Offer event-based promos (Valentine's, town fiestas, graduation season).
- Introduce loyalty cards or repeat customer discounts.
- Use bundle pricing to increase average spending per table.

4.3. Distribution Channels

- Strengthen delivery services within Marinduque municipalities.
- Accept orders via Facebook Messenger and mobile platforms.
- Expand catering services to schools, offices, and events.
- Partner with hotels and resorts for meal packages.

4.4. Promotional Efforts

- Use visual food marketing (high-quality photos and videos).
- Promote through Facebook groups and community pages.
- Encourage customer reviews and testimonials.
- Join local trade fairs and municipal events.
- Use tarpaulins and signage for strong local visibility.

C. Souvenir Shops

4.1. Product and Service Offering

- Use visual food marketing
- Diversify beyond Moriones-themed items (e.g., local delicacies, wearable crafts, everyday-use items).
- Develop season-neutral products that appeal to locals.
- Introduce innovative and affordable product lines.

- Explore customized and made-to-order souvenirs.
- Sustain wholesale production for resellers.

4.2. Pricing Strategy

- Apply competitive pricing for local buyers.
- Offer wholesale discounts and reseller rates.
- Provide bundle deals (e.g., souvenir sets).
- Adjust pricing strategically when booth and logistics costs increase.

4.3. Distribution Channels

- Expand through online selling platforms and Facebook Marketplace.
- Strengthen wholesale and reseller networks.
- Participate in trade fairs outside Marinduque.
- Explore partnerships with exporters and regional distributors.

4.4. Promotional Efforts

- Utilize storytelling marketing (heritage and craftsmanship narratives).
- Post consistent product features on social media.
- Offer limited-time discounts and freebies during slow months.
- Collaborate with tourism offices for display opportunities.
- Promote products as cultural identity items, not only festival souvenirs.

D. Tour Agencies

4.1. Product and Service Offering

- Diversify beyond Moriones packages (educational tours, heritage tours, island hopping, farm tourism).
- Offer event planning and logistics services.
- Develop local and outbound travel packages.
- Create experiential packages highlighting Marinduque culture year-round.

4.2. Pricing Strategy

- Introduce tiered package pricing (basic, standard, premium).
- Provide group booking discounts.
- Offer early-bird or off-season discounts.
- Bundle transportation, accommodation, and tours for value efficiency.

4.3. Distribution Channels

- Build a professional website with booking inquiry system.

- Use social media and travel platforms for marketing.
- Partner with hotels, restaurants, and LGUs.
- Target schools, corporations, and organizations for institutional tours.

4.4. Promotional Efforts

- Promote Marinduque beyond Moriones (eco-tourism, heritage, beaches).
- Share customer testimonials and tour highlights.
- Engage in regional tourism expos and trade fairs.
- Strengthen digital marketing (consistent posting, video content).
- Collaborate with influencers or travel bloggers.

Conclusions

1. The study concludes that local businesses associated with the Moriones Festival experience several challenges during the off-peak season, including low customer demand and occupancy, reduced sales, financial instability and seasonal income fluctuations, cost reduction and workforce challenges, uneven revenue distribution and government support concerns, and a shift in consumer behavior with limited local appreciation for culturally themed products. These challenges significantly affect operational stability, revenue generation, and the long-term sustainability of local enterprises.
2. The study further concludes that local businesses implement adaptive strategies across the marketing mix, particularly in Product and Service Offering, Pricing Strategy, Distribution Channels, and Promotional Efforts. These include maintaining product and service consistency, diversifying offerings, applying discounting and package deals, strengthening digital presence and distribution channels, and utilizing both digital and traditional promotional strategies. These practices reflect the operational flexibility of businesses in responding to seasonal tourism fluctuations.
3. The study also concludes that several growth opportunities exist for local businesses, including introducing new activities and experiences, improving customer service and overall experience, diversifying tour services, strengthening digitalization and online presence, expanding business partnerships, enhancing social media marketing, developing websites and e-commerce platforms, fostering promotional collaborations, and promoting the region beyond the Moriones Festival. These opportunities may help reduce seasonal dependence and enhance long-term competitiveness.
4. Finally, the study concludes that strategic marketing approaches can be developed to address off-peak season challenges through improvements in Product and Service Offering, Pricing Strategy, Distribution Channels, and Promotional Efforts. These strategies include experiential tourism offerings, value-based and seasonal pricing, expanded digital and partnership-based distribution channels, and

strengthened promotional campaigns that position Marinduque as a year-round destination. These initiatives may help stimulate off-season demand and support the sustainability of local businesses connected to the Moriones Festival.

Recommendations

Local Business Owners: Diversify products and services to maintain customer interest during off-peak seasons. Utilize digital marketing, social media, and e-commerce to reach broader audiences. Offering special deals, unique experiences, or collaborating with other businesses through joint promotions can help sustain sales year-round.

Local Employees: Cross-train in multiple roles to adapt to seasonal fluctuations. Performance-based incentives, career development opportunities, and wage increases linked to business performance can improve job satisfaction, retention, and overall contribution during slow periods.

Local Tourism Office: Promote off-season events, cultural activities, and workshops to attract visitors year-round. Collaborate with businesses on tourist packages and market the area as a year-round destination to reduce seasonal dependence.

Local Government and Policymakers: Provide financial support, tax relief, and infrastructure improvements to help businesses manage revenue fluctuations. Encourage digital innovation and marketing to enhance competitiveness and resilience.

Local Residents: Support local businesses throughout the year by visiting, recommending, and participating in off-season activities. Year-round patronage strengthens the community and contributes to economic stability.

Tourists: Promote off-season visits for quieter, more personalized experiences with lower costs and exclusive activities. Off-peak tourism supports local businesses while offering unique travel opportunities.

Academic Researchers and Students: Use the study as a reference for strategies sustaining businesses and tourism during off-peak periods. Future research can examine other regions facing seasonal challenges, providing insights for long-term local economic resilience.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical principles to ensure participants' safety, privacy, and well-being. All potential participants received an information letter explaining the study purpose, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Informed consent was obtained prior to data collection. Responses were kept confidential, personal data were anonymized, and interviews were recorded only with consent. Recordings and related materials were securely stored and accessible solely to the researcher. Although participants consented to the use of photographs and

marketing materials, pseudonyms are used in reporting to protect identities. Ethical transparency and participants' rights were maintained throughout, and participants were able to contact the researcher for any questions or concerns.

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